

**ON THE MINIMUM CARDINALITY OF GENERALIZED
SUMSETS IN FINITE CYCLIC GROUPS**

Jagannath Bhanja

*Harish-Chandra Research Institute, Chhatnag Road, Jhansi, Prayagraj, Uttar
Pradesh, India*

jagannathbhanja@hri.res.in

Received: 1/31/20, Revised: 10/3/20, Accepted: 12/20/20, Published: 2/1/21

Abstract

For a nonempty subset \mathcal{A} of an abelian group \mathcal{G} , the *generalized sumset* $h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}$ consists of all sums of h elements of \mathcal{A} with at most r repetitions for each element. In this paper, we generalize an earlier result of Bajnok on *restricted sumsets* $h^{(1)}\mathcal{A}$ in \mathbb{Z}_n to generalized sumsets $h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}$ in \mathbb{Z}_n for $1 \leq r \leq h$. More precisely, given positive integers h, r, k , we prove an upper bound for the minimum cardinality of $h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}$ when \mathcal{A} runs through all k -subsets of \mathbb{Z}_n . This is done by exactly calculating $|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}|$ for a very specific k -subset $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}_d(n, k)$ of \mathbb{Z}_n .

1. Introduction

Let \mathcal{G} be an abelian group written in additive notation. For a positive integer h and a nonempty finite subset \mathcal{A} of \mathcal{G} , we let $h\mathcal{A}$ and $h^\wedge\mathcal{A}$ be the *h -fold sumset* and the *h -fold restricted sumset* of \mathcal{A} , respectively; that is, $h\mathcal{A}$ is the collection of all sums of h not-necessarily-distinct elements of \mathcal{A} , and $h^\wedge\mathcal{A}$ is the collection of all sums of h distinct elements of \mathcal{A} . Clearly, in every element of $h\mathcal{A}$ an element of \mathcal{A} can appear at most h times, whereas it can appear at most once in every element of $h^\wedge\mathcal{A}$.

For given positive integers h, r with $r \leq h$, let $h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}$ be the collection of all sums of h elements of \mathcal{A} with at most r repetitions for each element. The sumset $h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}$ denote the *generalized sumset* of \mathcal{A} . Clearly, $h^{(h)}\mathcal{A} = h\mathcal{A}$ and $h^{(1)}\mathcal{A} = h^\wedge\mathcal{A}$. Therefore, $h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}$ is a natural generalization of $h\mathcal{A}$ and $h^\wedge\mathcal{A}$.

For a positive integer k ($\leq |\mathcal{G}|$), let

$$\mu(\mathcal{G}, k, h) := \min\{|h\mathcal{A}| : \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{G}, |\mathcal{A}| = k\},$$

$$h^\wedge(\mathcal{G}, k, h) := \min\{|h^\wedge\mathcal{A}| : \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{G}, |\mathcal{A}| = k\},$$

and

$$\mu^{(r)}(\mathcal{G}, k, h) := \min\{|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}| : \mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{G}, |\mathcal{A}| = k\}.$$

Given a nonempty subset \mathcal{A} of a finite abelian group \mathcal{G} , one of the important problems in *additive number theory* is to find the minimum cardinality of its sum-sets; that is, to find the exact value of the functions $\mu(\mathcal{G}, k, h)$, $\mu^\wedge(\mathcal{G}, k, h)$, and $\mu^{(r)}(\mathcal{G}, k, h)$ in terms of $|\mathcal{G}|$, k , h , and/or r .

The study of $\mu(\mathcal{G}, k, h)$ dates back to 1813, to one of the classical works of Cauchy [4], which gives the exact value of $\mu(\mathcal{G}, k, h)$ in cyclic groups of prime order. Later, in 1935, Davenport [5] (see also [6]) rediscovered Cauchy’s result. It is now known as the Cauchy-Davenport Theorem.

Theorem 1 (Cauchy-Davenport Theorem [4–6]). *Let \mathcal{A} be a nonempty k -subset of the group \mathbb{Z}_p , where p is a prime number. Then*

$$|h\mathcal{A}| \geq \min\{p, hk - h + 1\}.$$

This lower bound is tight for all values of k . Hence,

$$\mu(\mathbb{Z}_p, k, h) = \min\{p, hk - h + 1\}.$$

After several important but partial results proved in this direction, Eliahou, Kervaire, and Plagne [8] (see also [12, 13]) finally settled the general case by finding the exact value of $\mu(\mathcal{G}, k, h)$ in arbitrary finite abelian groups.

Theorem 2 (Eliahou, Kervaire, and Plagne [8]). *Let n , k , and h be positive integers with $k \leq n$. For any abelian group \mathcal{G} of order n , we have*

$$\mu(\mathcal{G}, k, h) = \phi(n, k, h),$$

where

$$\phi(n, k, h) := \min\{(h\lceil k/d \rceil - h + 1)d : d \in D(n)\},$$

and $D(n)$ is the set of positive divisors of n .

If $n = p$ is a prime number, then $\phi(p, k, h) = \min\{p, hk - h + 1\}$. Therefore, Theorem 2 is a generalization of the Cauchy-Davenport Theorem, i.e., Theorem 1.

In contrast to $\mu(\mathcal{G}, k, h)$, the function $\mu^\wedge(\mathcal{G}, k, h)$ is not well settled in general finite abelian groups. The exact value of $\mu^\wedge(\mathcal{G}, k, h)$ is known only in the cyclic groups of prime order. It was actually a conjecture of Erdős and Heilbronn [9] in 1964. In 1994, Dias da Silva and Hamidoune [7] proved this conjecture in its general form, that is, for all $h \geq 2$. They used some techniques from exterior algebra and representation theory. A year later the same conjecture was reproved by Alon, Nathanson, and Ruzsa [1, 2] using a more simple but powerful method, called the *polynomial method*.

Theorem 3 (Dias da Silva and Hamidoune [7]). *Let \mathcal{A} be a nonempty k -subset of the group \mathbb{Z}_p , where p is a prime number. Then*

$$|h^\wedge \mathcal{A}| \geq \min\{p, hk - h^2 + 1\}.$$

This bound is tight for all values of k . Therefore,

$$\mu^\wedge(\mathbb{Z}_p, k, h) = \min\{p, hk - h^2 + 1\}.$$

It is very difficult to find the exact value of $\mu^\wedge(\mathcal{G}, k, h)$ in general finite abelian groups, as in contrast to $\mu(\mathcal{G}, k, h)$, $\mu^\wedge(\mathcal{G}, k, h)$ depends on both cardinality and structure of the group \mathcal{G} .

In a recent study Bajnok [3] obtained an upper bound for the function $\mu^\wedge(\mathbb{Z}_n, k, h)$ by calculating the exact cardinality of a very specific set, which we define below.

For a given positive divisor d of n , we write k as $k = ud + v$ with $1 \leq v \leq d$, and set

$$\mathcal{A}_d(n, k) = \bigcup_{i=0}^{u-1} (i + \mathcal{H}) \cup \left\{ u + j \cdot \frac{n}{d} : j = 0, 1, \dots, v - 1 \right\}, \tag{1}$$

where $\mathcal{H} = \{0, n/d, \dots, (d - 1)(n/d)\}$ is the unique subgroup of order d in \mathbb{Z}_n . Clearly, $|\mathcal{A}_d(n, k)| = k$, and the set $\mathcal{A}_d(n, k)$ lies in exactly $\lceil k/d \rceil$ cosets of \mathcal{H} . Since $k \leq n$, we have $u < n/d$. Thus, the set $\mathcal{A}_d(n, k)$ has k distinct elements.

Theorem 4 (Bajnok [3]). *Let n , k , and h be positive integers with $k \leq n$. Let d be a positive divisor of n .*

If $h = k$, then $|h^\wedge \mathcal{A}_d(n, k)| = 1$, and if $h > k$, then $|h^\wedge \mathcal{A}_d(n, k)| = 0$.

For $1 \leq h \leq k - 1$, let v and w be the positive remainders of k and h modulo d , respectively. Then

$$|h^\wedge \mathcal{A}_d(n, k)| = \begin{cases} \min\{n, (h \lceil \frac{k}{d} \rceil - h + 1)d, hk - h^2 + 1\} & \text{if } h \leq \min\{v, d - 1\}; \\ \min\{n, hk - h^2 + 1 - \delta_d\} & \text{otherwise;} \end{cases}$$

where δ_d is the correction term defined by

$$\delta_d = \begin{cases} (v - w)w - (d - 1) & \text{if } w < v, \\ (d - w)(w - v) - (d - 1) & \text{if } v < w < d, \\ d - 1 & \text{if } v = w = d, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Thus, by setting

$$\phi^\wedge(n, k, h) := \min\{|h^\wedge \mathcal{A}_d(n, k)| : d \in D(n)\},$$

one has

$$\mu^\wedge(\mathbb{Z}_n, k, h) \leq \phi^\wedge(n, k, h).$$

Turning now to the generalized sumset, $h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}$ was introduced by Mistri and Pandey [10] in 2014. They obtained the minimum cardinality of $h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}$ for all k , h , and r , when \mathcal{A} is a finite set of k integers. A year later Monopoli [11] proved a similar result when \mathcal{A} is a nonempty subset of the group \mathbb{Z}_p , where p is a prime number.

Theorem 5 (Monopoli [11]). *Let h and r be positive integers such that $h = mr + \epsilon$ with $0 \leq \epsilon < r$. Let $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathbb{Z}_p$ be a nonempty set with $|\mathcal{A}| = k$ and $rk \geq h$. Then*

$$|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}| \geq \min\{p, hk - m^2r + 1 - (2m + 1)\epsilon\}.$$

This lower bound is tight for all values of h , r , and k , which can be seen by taking an arithmetic progression. Hence,

$$\mu^{(r)}(\mathbb{Z}_p, k, h) = \min\{p, hk - m^2r + 1 - (2m + 1)\epsilon\}.$$

In this article we give an upper bound for the function $\mu^{(r)}(\mathbb{Z}_n, k, h)$ for all n , k , and h , which we obtain by exactly calculating $|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d(n, k)|$. This computation is very similar to Bajnok’s proof of Theorem 4. We use the following lemma of Bajnok (see Lemma 14, [3]) to achieve our results.

Lemma 1 (Bajnok [3]). *Let d and t be positive integers with $t \leq d - 1$, and let $j \in \mathbb{Z}_d$. Then there is a t -subset $J = \{j_1, \dots, j_t\}$ of \mathbb{Z}_d for which $j_1 + \dots + j_t = j$.*

2. Main Results

Let \mathcal{A} be a nonempty k -subset of \mathbb{Z}_n . Let h, r be positive integers with $r \leq h$. Set $h = mr + \epsilon$, where $0 \leq \epsilon < r$. So, by the definition of $h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}$ we have $|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}| = 1$ if $h = rk$, and $|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}| = 0$ if $h > rk$. Therefore, we assume that $1 \leq h \leq rk - 1$. This implies $1 \leq m \leq k - 1$.

2.1. The case $\epsilon = 0$

Theorem 6. *Let n, k, h, m , and r be positive integers such that $k \leq n$ and $h = mr$. For a fixed positive divisor d of n , let $\mathcal{A}_d(n, k)$ be the set defined in (1). Let v and w be the positive remainders of k and m modulo d , respectively. Then*

$$|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d(n, k)| = \begin{cases} \min\{n, (h\lceil k/d \rceil - h + 1)d, hk - m^2r + 1\} & \text{if } m \leq \min\{v, d - 1\}; \\ \min\{n, hk - m^2r + 1 - \delta_d\} & \text{otherwise;} \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

where

$$\delta_d = \begin{cases} r(v - w)w - (d - 1) & \text{if } w < v, \\ r(d - w)(w - v) - (d - 1) & \text{if } v < w < d, \\ d - 1 & \text{if } v = w = d, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Proof. Set

$$k = ud + v \text{ with } u = \left\lfloor \frac{k}{d} \right\rfloor - 1$$

and

$$m = qd + w \text{ with } q = \left\lceil \frac{m}{d} \right\rceil - 1,$$

where $u \geq 0, q \geq 0, 1 \leq v \leq d$, and $1 \leq w \leq d$. Recall the set

$$\mathcal{A}_d = \mathcal{A}_d(n, k) = \bigcup_{i=0}^{u-1} (i + \mathcal{H}) \cup \left\{ u + j \cdot \frac{n}{d} : j = 0, 1, \dots, v-1 \right\},$$

where $\mathcal{H} = \{0, n/d, \dots, (d-1)(n/d)\}$.

Clearly, every element of $h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d$ is of the form

$$(i_1 + \dots + i_h) + (j_1 + \dots + j_h) \cdot \frac{n}{d},$$

where $i_1, \dots, i_h \in \{0, 1, \dots, u\}$ and $j_1, \dots, j_h \in \{0, 1, \dots, d-1\}$, with the added conditions

- (i) when any of the i -indices equals u , the corresponding j -index is at most $v-1$,
- (ii) corresponding to one i -index we can have at most r same j -index.

The least value i_{min} of $i_1 + \dots + i_h$ is

$$i_{min} = rd(0 + 1 + \dots + (q-1)) + rqw = rq(m + w - d)/2.$$

To compute the largest value i_{max} of $i_1 + \dots + i_h$ we consider the following four possible cases.

First, let $q = 0$ and $w > v$. Then $m = w > v$ and $1 \leq m - v \leq d - 1$. Thus,

$$i_{max} = ruv + r(m - v)(u - 1) = r(mu - m + v).$$

Next, let $q = 0$ and $w \leq v$. Then $m = w \leq v$. Thus,

$$i_{max} = mru = r(mu - m + w).$$

Now, let $q \geq 1$ and $w > v$. By writing m as $m = v + dq + (w - v)$ we get

$$\begin{aligned} i_{max} &= ruv + r((u-1) + \dots + (u-q))d + r(w-v)(u-q-1) \\ &= r(mu - m + qv - q(m+w-d)/2 + v). \end{aligned}$$

Finally, let $q \geq 1$ and $w \leq v$. Then $1 \leq d + w - v \leq d$. By writing m as $m = v + d(q-1) + (d+w-v)$ we get

$$\begin{aligned} i_{max} &= ruv + r((u-1) + \dots + (u-q+1))d + r(d+w-v)(u-q) \\ &= r(mu - m + qv - q(m+w-d)/2 + w). \end{aligned}$$

All the above four cases can be written in the unified form

$$i_{max} = r(mu - m + qv - q(m + w - d)/2 + \min\{v, w\}).$$

Since $i = i_1 + \dots + i_h$ can assume any integer value between i_{min} and i_{max} , the sumset $h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d$ lies exactly in $\min\{n/d, i_{max} - i_{min} + 1\}$ cosets of \mathcal{H} . This gives

$$|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| \leq \min\{n, (i_{max} - i_{min} + 1)d\},$$

where

$$(i_{max} - i_{min} + 1)d = hk - m^2r - r(v - w)w + rd \cdot \min\{0, v - w\} + d.$$

If $m = 1$, then $r = h$. Therefore,

$$h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d = h\mathcal{A}_d = \bigcup_{i=0}^{hu-1} (i + \mathcal{H}) \cup \left\{ hu + j \cdot \frac{n}{d} : j = 0, 1, \dots, h(v - 1) \right\}.$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} |h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| &= \min\{n, hud + \min\{d, hv - h + 1\}\} \\ &= \min\{n, (hu + 1)d, hk - h + 1\} \\ &= \min\{n, (h\lceil k/d \rceil - h + 1)d, hk - h + 1\}. \end{aligned}$$

This satisfies (2).

Now, assume that $2 \leq m \leq k - 1$. We compute $|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d|$ in the following possible cases.

Case 1. Let $m \leq v$ and $m < d$. This implies $i_{min} = 0$ and $i_{max} = mru = hu$. So, by Lemma 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d &= \bigcup_{i=0}^{hu-1} (i + \mathcal{H}) \\ &\quad \cup \left\{ hu + j \cdot \frac{n}{d} : j = mr(m - 1)/2, \dots, mr(v - 1) - mr(m - 1)/2 \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} |h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| &= \min\{n, hud + \min\{d, mr(v - 1) - mr(m - 1) + 1\}\} \\ &= \min\{n, (hu + 1)d, hk - m^2r + 1\} \\ &= \min\{n, (h\lceil k/d \rceil - h + 1)d, hk - m^2r + 1\}. \end{aligned}$$

Case 2. Let $m = v = d$. Then $q = 0$ and $w = m = d$. This implies $i_{min} = 0$ and $i_{max} = mru = hu$. Since $m < k = ud + v = ud + m$, we have $u \geq 1$. Thus,

$$h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d = \left\{ \frac{mr(m - 1)}{2} \cdot \frac{n}{d} \right\} \bigcup_{i=1}^{hu-1} (i + \mathcal{H}) \cup \left\{ hu + \frac{mr(m - 1)}{2} \cdot \frac{n}{d} \right\}.$$

If $hu - 1 \geq n/d$, then

$$|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| = n = \min\{n, hk - m^2r - m + 2\},$$

as

$$\begin{aligned} hk - m^2r - m + 2 &= mr(ud + v) - m^2r - m + 2 \\ &= mrud - m + 2 \\ &\geq d(n/d + 1) - m + 2 \\ &= n + 2 \\ &> n. \end{aligned}$$

If $hu - 1 \leq n/d - 2$, then

$$|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| = (hu - 1)d + 2 = hk - m^2r - m + 2 = \min\{n, hk - m^2r - m + 2\},$$

as $hk - m^2r - m + 2 = (hu - 1)d + 2 \leq (n/d - 2)d + 2 \leq n$.

Now, let $hu - 1 = n/d - 1$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d &= \left\{ \frac{mr(m-1)}{2} \cdot \frac{n}{d} \right\} \bigcup_{i=1}^{hu-1} (i + \mathcal{H}) \bigcup \left\{ hu + \frac{mr(m-1)}{2} \cdot \frac{n}{d} \right\} \\ &= \bigcup_{i=1}^{n/d-1} (i + \mathcal{H}) \bigcup \left\{ j \cdot \frac{n}{d} : j = \frac{mr(m-1)}{2}, \frac{mr(m-1)}{2} + 1 \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| = (n/d - 1)d + 2 = (hu - 1)d + 2 = hk - m^2r - m + 2.$$

Since $hk - m^2r - m + 2 = (n/d - 1)d + 2 = n - (d - 2)$ and $d = m \geq 2$, we get

$$|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| = hk - m^2r - m + 2 = \min\{n, hk - m^2r - m + 2\}.$$

Case 3. Let $m > v$, $w \neq d$, and $w \neq v$. So, by Lemma 1, we have

$$h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d = \bigcup_{i=i_{min}}^{i_{max}} (i + \mathcal{H}).$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} |h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| &= \min\{n, (i_{max} - i_{min} + 1)d\} \\ &= \min\{n, hk - m^2r - r(v - w)w + rd \cdot \min\{0, v - w\} + d\}. \end{aligned}$$

Case 4. Let $m > v$, $w = d$, and $w \neq v$. Then $m = (q + 1)d$ and $k = ud + v$ with $1 \leq v < d$. So, by Lemma 1, we have

$$h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d = \{x_{min}\} \bigcup_{i=i_{min}+1}^{i_{max}} (i + \mathcal{H}),$$

where x_{min} is the sum of all elements of $\bigcup_{i=0}^q (i + \mathcal{H})$ with each element repeating exactly r -times. Hence,

$$|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| = \min\{n, (i_{max} - i_{min})d + 1\} = \min\{n, hk - m^2r + 1\}.$$

Case 5. Let $m > v$, $w \neq d$, and $w = v$. Then, Lemma 1 implies

$$h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d = \bigcup_{i=i_{min}}^{i_{max}-1} (i + \mathcal{H}) \bigcup \{x_{max}\},$$

where x_{max} is the sum of all elements of

$$\bigcup_{i=u-q}^{u-1} (i + \mathcal{H}) \bigcup \left\{ u + j \cdot \frac{n}{d} : j = 0, 1, \dots, v - 1 \right\}$$

with each element repeating exactly r -times. Hence,

$$|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| = \min\{n, (i_{max} - i_{min})d + 1\} = \min\{n, hk - m^2r + 1\}.$$

Case 6. Let $m > v$ and $w = v = d$. So, by Lemma 1, we have

$$h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d = \{x_{min}\} \bigcup_{i=i_{min}+1}^{i_{max}-1} (i + \mathcal{H}) \bigcup \{x_{max}\},$$

where x_{min} and x_{max} are defined in Case 4 and Case 5, respectively.

Since $w = v = d$, we get $(i_{max} - i_{min} - 1)d = hk - m^2r - d$. We consider the following three subcases.

Subcase (i). Let $k > n/mr + m$. Then $i_{max} - i_{min} - 1 > n/d - 1$. Since it is an integer, we get $i_{max} - i_{min} - 1 \geq n/d$. Thus,

$$|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| = n = \min\{n, hk - m^2r - d + 2\},$$

as $hk - m^2r - d + 2 = (i_{max} - i_{min} - 1)d + 2 \geq (n/d)d + 2 = n + 2 > n$.

Subcase (ii). Let $k < n/mr + m$. Then $i_{max} - i_{min} - 1 < n/d - 1$, and thus at most $n/d - 2$. Therefore,

$$|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| = (i_{max} - i_{min} - 1)d + 2 = hk - m^2r - d + 2 = \min\{n, hk - m^2r - d + 2\},$$

as $hk - m^2r - d + 2 = (i_{max} - i_{min} - 1)d + 2 \leq (n/d - 2)d + 2 = n - 2d + 2 \leq n$.

Subcase (iii). Let $k = n/mr + m$. Then $i_{max} - i_{min} = n/d$. So,

$$\begin{aligned} h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d &= \{x_{min}\} \bigcup_{i=i_{min}+1}^{i_{max}-1} (i + \mathcal{H}) \bigcup \{x_{max}\} \\ &= \bigcup_{i=i_{min}+1}^{i_{min}+n/d-1} (i + \mathcal{H}) \bigcup \{x_{min}, x_{max}\}. \end{aligned}$$

From the definition, we have

$$x_{min} = \frac{rdq(q+1)}{2} + \frac{rd(d-1)(q+1)}{2} \cdot \frac{n}{d}$$

and

$$x_{max} = rud(q+1) - \frac{rdq(q+1)}{2} + \frac{rd(d-1)(q+1)}{2} \cdot \frac{n}{d}.$$

But,

$$ud = k - d = \frac{n}{mr} + m - d = \frac{n}{rd(q+1)} + dq.$$

This implies

$$x_{max} = \frac{rdq(q+1)}{2} + \left(\frac{rd(d-1)(q+1)}{2} + 1 \right) \cdot \frac{n}{d}.$$

We note that $x_{min} = x_{max}$ if and only if $d = 1$. Thus, if $d = 1$, then

$$|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| = \left(\frac{n}{d} - 1\right)d + 1 = n = \min\{n, hk - m^2r - d + 2\},$$

as $hk - m^2r - d + 2 = n - d + 2 = n + 1 > n$. If $d \geq 2$, then

$$|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| = \left(\frac{n}{d} - 1\right)d + 2 = n - d + 2 = \min\{n, hk - m^2r - d + 2\},$$

as $hk - m^2r - d + 2 = n - d + 2 \leq n$.

This completes the Case 6, and also completes the proof of the theorem. □

Remark 1. As a particular case of Theorem 6, for $r = 1$, we obtain Theorem 4.

Remark 2. When $n = p$ is a prime number, Theorem 6 gives

$$|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}| \leq \min\{p, hk - m^2r + 1\}.$$

This upper bound is exactly the same as the lower bound obtained in Theorem 5, in the case $\epsilon = 0$.

2.2. The Case $\epsilon \geq 1$

Theorem 7. *Let $n, k, h, m,$ and r be positive integers such that $k \leq n$ and $h = mr + \epsilon$ with $1 \leq \epsilon < r$. For a fixed positive divisor d of n , let $\mathcal{A}_d(n, k)$ be the set defined in (1). Let v and w be the positive remainders of k and m modulo d , respectively. Then*

$$|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d(n, k)| = \begin{cases} \min\{n, (h\lceil k/d \rceil - h + 1)d, hk - m^2r + 1 - (2m + 1)\epsilon\} & \text{if } m < v \leq d; \\ \min\{n, (h\lceil k/d \rceil - h + 1)d - \epsilon d\} & \text{if } m = v < d; \\ \min\{n, hk - m^2r + 1 - (2m + 1)\epsilon - (m - 1)(\epsilon - 1)\} & \text{if } m = v = d; \\ \min\{n, hk - m^2r + 1 - (2m + 1)\epsilon - \delta_d\} & \text{if } m > v; \end{cases}$$

where

$$\delta_d = \begin{cases} r(v - w)w - (d - 1) + (v - 2w - 1)\epsilon & \text{if } w < v \leq d, \\ r(d - w)(w - v) - (d - 1) + (v - 2w + d - 1)\epsilon & \text{if } v < w < d, \\ -(d - 1) + (v - 2w + d - 1)\epsilon & \text{if } v = w < d, \\ -(d - 1) + (v - 2w + 2d - 1)\epsilon & \text{if } w = d. \end{cases}$$

Proof. Recall the notations

$$h = mr + \epsilon \text{ with } m = \left\lfloor \frac{h}{r} \right\rfloor,$$

$$k = ud + v \text{ with } u = \left\lfloor \frac{k}{d} \right\rfloor - 1,$$

and

$$m = qd + w \text{ with } q = \left\lfloor \frac{m}{d} \right\rfloor - 1,$$

where $m \geq 1, u \geq 0, q \geq 0, 1 \leq \epsilon < r, 1 \leq v \leq d,$ and $1 \leq w \leq d$. Recall also that the set

$$\mathcal{A}_d = \mathcal{A}_d(n, k) = \bigcup_{i=0}^{u-1} (i + \mathcal{H}) \cup \left\{ u + j \cdot \frac{n}{d} : j = 0, 1, \dots, v - 1 \right\},$$

where $\mathcal{H} = \{0, n/d, \dots, (d - 1)(n/d)\}$.

Similar to the proof of Theorem 6, every element of $h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d$ is of the form

$$(i_1 + \dots + i_h) + (j_1 + \dots + j_h) \cdot \frac{n}{d},$$

where $i_1, \dots, i_h \in \{0, 1, \dots, u\}$ and $j_1, \dots, j_h \in \{0, 1, \dots, d - 1\}$, with the added conditions

- (i) when any of the i -indices equals u , the corresponding j -index is at most $v - 1$,
- (ii) corresponding to one i -index we can have at most r same j -index.

We compute the least value i_{min} of $i_1 + \dots + i_h$ in the following possible cases.

First, let $w < v$. Then $h = mr + \epsilon = rdq + rw + \epsilon$. Since $\epsilon < r \leq r(v - w)$, we get $rw + \epsilon < rv$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} i_{min} &= rd(0 + 1 + \dots + (q - 1)) + (rw + \epsilon)q \\ &= rq((q - 1)d + 2w)/2 + \epsilon q \\ &= rq(qd + w + w - d)/2 + \epsilon q \\ &= rq(m + w - d)/2 + \epsilon q. \end{aligned}$$

Next, let $w = v$. Then $h = mr + \epsilon = rdq + rw + \epsilon = rdq + rv + \epsilon$. If $v = d$, then

$$\begin{aligned} i_{min} &= rd(0 + 1 + \dots + q) + \epsilon(q + 1) \\ &= rq(q + 1)d/2 + \epsilon(q + 1) \\ &= rqm/2 + \epsilon(q + 1) \\ &= rq(m + w - d)/2 + \epsilon(q + 1). \end{aligned}$$

If $v < d$, then $rv + \epsilon < rv + r = r(v + 1) \leq rd$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} i_{min} &= rd(0 + 1 + \dots + (q - 1)) + (rv + \epsilon)q \\ &= rq((q - 1)d + 2v)/2 + \epsilon q \\ &= rq(qd + v + v - d)/2 + \epsilon q \\ &= rq(m + v - d)/2 + \epsilon q \\ &= rq(m + w - d)/2 + \epsilon q. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, let $w > v$. If $w = d$, then

$$i_{min} = rd(0 + 1 + \dots + q) + \epsilon(q + 1) = rq(m + w - d)/2 + \epsilon(q + 1).$$

If $w < d$, then $rw + \epsilon < r(d - 1) + r = rd$. Therefore,

$$i_{min} = rd(0 + 1 + \dots + (q - 1)) + (rw + \epsilon)q = rq(m + w - d)/2 + \epsilon q.$$

The above three cases of i_{min} can be written in the unified form

$$i_{min} = \begin{cases} rq(m + w - d)/2 + \epsilon q & \text{if } w < d, \\ rq(m + w - d)/2 + \epsilon(q + 1) & \text{if } w = d. \end{cases}$$

Now, we compute the largest value i_{max} of $i_1 + \dots + i_h$ in the following possible cases.

First, let $q = 0$ and $w > v$. Then $m = w > v$ and $1 \leq m - v \leq d - 1$. Therefore,

$$h = mr + \epsilon = rw + \epsilon = rv + r(w - v) + \epsilon$$

with

$$r(w - v) + \epsilon < r(m - v) + r \leq r(d - 1) + r = rd.$$

Hence,

$$i_{max} = ruv + (r(w - v) + \epsilon)(u - 1) = r(mu - m + v) + \epsilon(u - 1).$$

Next, let $q = 0$ and $w = v$. Then $m = w = v$ and $h = mr + \epsilon = rv + \epsilon$. Therefore,

$$i_{max} = ruv + \epsilon(u - 1) = r(mu - m + v) + \epsilon(u - 1).$$

Now, let $q = 0$ and $w < v$. Then $m = w < v$ and $h = mr + \epsilon < (v - 1)r + r = vr$. Thus,

$$i_{max} = (mr + \epsilon)u = r(mu - m + w) + \epsilon u.$$

Next, let $q \geq 1$ and $w > v$. Then $w - v + 1 \leq d$. By writing m as $m = dq + w = v + dq + (w - v)$ we get $h = vr + dq + (w - v)r + \epsilon$, with $(w - v)r + \epsilon < (w - v + 1)r \leq rd$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} i_{max} &= ruv + rd((u - 1) + \dots + (u - q)) + ((w - v)r + \epsilon)(u - q - 1) \\ &= r(mu - m + vq - q(m + w - d)/2 + v) + \epsilon(u - q - 1). \end{aligned}$$

Next, let $q \geq 1$ and $w = v$. Then $m = dq + v$ and $h = vr + dq + \epsilon$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} i_{max} &= ruv + rd((u - 1) + \dots + (u - q)) + \epsilon(u - q - 1) \\ &= r(mu - m + vq - q(m + w - d)/2 + v) + \epsilon(u - q - 1). \end{aligned}$$

Finally, let $q \geq 1$ and $w < v$. Then $1 \leq d + w - v \leq d - 1$. By writing m as $m = v + d(q - 1) + (d + w - v)$ we get $h = vr + (q - 1)dr + (d + w - v)r + \epsilon$, with $(d + w - v)r + \epsilon < (d - 1)r + r = rd$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} i_{max} &= ruv + rd((u - 1) + \dots + (u - q + 1)) + ((d + w - v)r + \epsilon)(u - q) \\ &= r(mu - m + vq - q(m + w - d)/2 + w) + \epsilon(u - q). \end{aligned}$$

All the above six possible values of i_{max} can be written in the unified form

$$i_{max} = \begin{cases} r(mu - m + vq - q(m + w - d)/2 + w) + \epsilon(u - q) & \text{if } w < v, \\ r(mu - m + vq - q(m + w - d)/2 + v) + \epsilon(u - q - 1) & \text{if } w \geq v. \end{cases}$$

Since $i = i_1 + \dots + i_h$ can assume any integer value between i_{min} and i_{max} , the sumset $h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d$ lies exactly in $\min\{n/d, i_{max} - i_{min} + 1\}$ cosets of \mathcal{H} . This implies

$$|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| \leq \min\{n, (i_{max} - i_{min} + 1)d\}.$$

Note that, if $w = d$, then

$$\begin{aligned} & (i_{max} - i_{min} + 1)d \\ &= \left(mru - mr + rvq - \frac{mrq}{2} + rv + \epsilon(u - q - 1) - \frac{mrq}{2} - \epsilon(q + 1) + 1 \right) d \\ &= mrud - mr(q + 1)d + rv(q + 1)d + \epsilon ud - \epsilon(2q + 2)d + d \\ &= (mr + \epsilon)ud - m^2r + mrv + d - \epsilon(2q + 2)d \\ &= (mr + \epsilon)(ud + v) - m^2r - \epsilon v + d - \epsilon(2q + 2)d \\ &= hk - m^2r + d - \epsilon((2q + 2)d + v). \end{aligned}$$

If $w < d$, then

$$\begin{aligned} & (i_{max} - i_{min} + 1)d \\ &= \begin{cases} hk - m^2r - r(v - w)w + d - \epsilon(2qd + v) & \text{if } w < v, \\ hk - m^2r - r(w - v)(d - w) + d - \epsilon((2q + 1)d + v) & \text{if } w \geq v. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Now we are ready to compute $|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d|$.

Case 1: Let $m = v < d$. Then $q = 0$ and $m = w = v < d$. This implies $i_{min} = 0$ and $i_{max} = ruv + \epsilon(u - 1) = mru + \epsilon(u - 1) = hu - \epsilon$. So, by Lemma 1, we have

$$h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d = \bigcup_{i=0}^{hu-\epsilon} (i + \mathcal{H}).$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} |h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| &= \min\{n, (hu - \epsilon + 1)d\} \\ &= \min\{n, (hu + 1)d - \epsilon d\} \\ &= \min\{n, (h\lceil k/d \rceil - h + 1)d - \epsilon d\}. \end{aligned}$$

Case 2: Let $m < v \leq d$. Then $q = 0$ and $m = w$. This implies $i_{min} = 0$ and $i_{max} = (mr + \epsilon)u = hu$. So, by Lemma 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d &= \bigcup_{i=0}^{hu-1} (i + \mathcal{H}) \cup \\ & \left\{ hu + j \cdot \frac{n}{d} : j = \frac{mr(m-1)}{2} + \epsilon m, \dots, mr(v-1) - \frac{mr(m-1)}{2} + \epsilon(v-m-1) \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} |h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| &= \min\{n, hud + \min\{d, mr(v - m) + (v - 2m - 1)\epsilon + 1\}\} \\ &= \min\{n, (hu + 1)d, hk - m^2r - (2m + 1)\epsilon + 1\} \\ &= \min\{n, (h\lceil k/d \rceil - h + 1)d, hk - m^2r + 1 - (2m + 1)\epsilon\}. \end{aligned}$$

Case 3: Let $m = v = d$. Then $q = 0$ and $w = m = v = d$. This implies $i_{min} = \epsilon$ and $i_{max} = mru + \epsilon(u - 1) = hu - \epsilon$. So, by Lemma 1, we have

$$h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d = \bigcup_{i=\epsilon}^{hu-\epsilon} (i + \mathcal{H}).$$

If $hu - 2\epsilon + 1 \geq n/d$, then

$$\begin{aligned} |h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| &= n \\ &= \min\{n, hk - m^2r + (1 - 3\epsilon)m\} \\ &= \min\{n, hk - m^2r + 1 - (2m + 1)\epsilon - (m - 1)(\epsilon - 1)\}, \end{aligned}$$

as

$$\begin{aligned} hk - m^2r + (1 - 3\epsilon)m &= (mr + \epsilon)(ud + v) - m^2r + (1 - 3\epsilon)m \\ &= mru + \epsilon ud + (1 - 2\epsilon)m \\ &= mru + \epsilon ud + (1 - 2\epsilon)d \\ &= (hu - 2\epsilon + 1)d \\ &\geq n. \end{aligned}$$

If $hu - 2\epsilon + 1 \leq n/d - 1$, then

$$\begin{aligned} |h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| &= (hu - 2\epsilon + 1)d \\ &= hk - m^2r + (1 - 3\epsilon)m \\ &= hk - m^2r + 1 - (2m + 1)\epsilon - (m - 1)(\epsilon - 1) \\ &= \min\{n, hk - m^2r + 1 - (2m + 1)\epsilon - (m - 1)(\epsilon - 1)\}, \end{aligned}$$

as

$$\begin{aligned} hk - m^2r + 1 - (2m + 1)\epsilon - (m - 1)(\epsilon - 1) &= (hu - 2\epsilon + 1)d \\ &\leq (n/d - 1)d \\ &= n - d \\ &< n. \end{aligned}$$

Case 4: Let $m > v$, $w \neq d$, and $w \neq v$. Then, Lemma 1 implies

$$h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d = \bigcup_{i=i_{min}}^{i_{max}} (i + \mathcal{H}).$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned}
 |h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| &= \min\{n, (i_{max} - i_{min} + 1)d\} \\
 &= \begin{cases} \min\{n, hk - m^2r - r(v - w)w + d - \epsilon(2qd + v)\} & \text{if } w < v, \\ \min\{n, hk - m^2r - r(w - v)(d - w) + d - \epsilon((2q + 1)d + v)\} & \text{if } w > v. \end{cases} \\
 &= \begin{cases} \min\{n, hk - m^2r - (2m + 1)\epsilon - r(v - w)w + d - (v - 2w - 1)\epsilon\} & \text{if } w < v, \\ \min\{n, hk - m^2r - (2m + 1)\epsilon - r(v - w)(w - d) + d - (v - 2w + d - 1)\epsilon\} & \text{if } w > v. \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

Case 5: Let $m > v$, $w = d$, and $w \neq v$. Then $h = (q + 1)d + \epsilon$ and $k = ud + v$ with $1 \leq v < d$. So, by Lemma 1, we have

$$h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d = \bigcup_{i=i_{min}}^{i_{max}} (i + \mathcal{H}).$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned}
 |h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| &= \min\{n, (i_{max} - i_{min} + 1)d\} \\
 &= \min\{n, hk - m^2r + d - \epsilon((2q + 2)d + v)\} \\
 &= \min\{n, hk - m^2r - (2m + 1)\epsilon + d - (v - 2w + 2d - 1)\epsilon\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Case 6: Let $m > v$, $w \neq d$, and $w = v$. Then, Lemma 1 implies

$$h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d = \bigcup_{i=i_{min}}^{i_{max}} (i + \mathcal{H}).$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned}
 |h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| &= \min\{n, (i_{max} - i_{min} + 1)d\} \\
 &= \min\{n, hk - m^2r + d - \epsilon((2q + 1)d + v)\} \\
 &= \min\{n, hk - m^2r - (2m + 1)\epsilon + d - (v - 2w + d - 1)\epsilon\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Case 7: Let $m > v$ and $w = v = d$. By Lemma 1, we have

$$h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d = \bigcup_{i=i_{min}}^{i_{max}} (i + \mathcal{H}).$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned}
 |h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d| &= \min\{n, (i_{max} - i_{min} + 1)d\} \\
 &= \min\{n, hk - m^2r + d - \epsilon((2q + 2)d + v)\} \\
 &= \min\{n, hk - m^2r - (2m + 1)\epsilon + d - (v - 2w + 2d - 1)\epsilon\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of the theorem. □

As an analogue of the function $\phi(n, k, h)$ and $\phi^\wedge(n, k, h)$, let us define the function

$$\phi^{(r)}(n, k, h) := \min\{|h^{(r)}\mathcal{A}_d(n, k)| : d \in D(n)\}.$$

So, by Theorem 6 and Theorem 7, we have

$$\mu^{(r)}(\mathbb{Z}_n, k, h) \leq \phi^{(r)}(n, k, h).$$

Acknowledgement. The author would like to thank the anonymous referee for his/her valuable and constructive comments, that helped the author to present the paper in a better form.

References

- [1] N. Alon, M. B. Nathanson, and I. Ruzsa, Adding distinct congruence classes modulo a prime, *Amer. Math. Monthly* **102** (1995), 250–255.
- [2] N. Alon, M. B. Nathanson, and I. Ruzsa, The polynomial method and restricted sums of congruence classes, *J. Number Theory* **56** (1996), 404–417.
- [3] B. Bajnok, On the minimum cardinality of restricted sumsets in cyclic groups, *Acta Math. Hungar.* **148** (1) (2016), 228–256.
- [4] A. L. Cauchy, Recherches sur les nombres, *J. École Polytech.* **9** (1813), 99–116.
- [5] H. Davenport, On the addition of residue classes, *J. Lond. Math. Soc.* **10** (1935), 30–32.
- [6] H. Davenport, A historical note, *J. Lond. Math. Soc.* **22** (1947), 100–101.
- [7] J. A. Dias da Silva and Y. O. Hamidoune, Cyclic space for Grassmann derivatives and additive theory, *Bull. Lond. Math. Soc.* **26** (1994), 140–146.
- [8] S. Eliahou, M. Kervaire, and A. Plagne, Optimally small sumsets in finite Abelian groups, *J. Number Theory* **101** (2003), 338–348.
- [9] P. Erdős and H. Heilbronn, On the addition of residue classes (mod p), *Acta Arith.* **9** (1964), 149–159.
- [10] R. K. Mistri and R. K. Pandey, A generalization of sumsets of sets of integers, *J. Number Theory* **143** (2014), 334–356.
- [11] F. Monopoli, A generalization of sumsets modulo a prime, *J. Number Theory* **157** (2015), 271–279.
- [12] A. Plagne, Optimally small sumsets in groups, I. The supersmall sumset property, the $\mu_G^{(k)}$ and the $\nu_G^{(k)}$ functions, *Unif. Distrib. Theory* **1** (1) (2006), 27–44.
- [13] A. Plagne, Optimally small sumsets in groups, II. The hypersmall sumset property and restricted addition, *Unif. Distrib. Theory* **1** (1) (2006), 111–124.